

Supplementary Material S1. Overview of the chronologies of all cultural periods and cultural stages associated with the archaeological sites analysed in the current study. Stages of cultural periods are shown in parentheses.

Name of cultural period/stage	Start age (cal BP)	End age (cal BP)
Siraya	500	300
North Jiushe	600	200
Jingpu	600	200
Paiwan	1000	100
Mao'ergan	1000	350
Fanzaiyuan (Luliao)	1000	350
Niaosung (Kanxi)	1000	500
Niaosong (Niaosong)	1400	1000
Yuanli	1500	400
Funan	1500	500
Fanzaiyuan, undifferentiated	1600	350
Fanzaiyuan (Fanzaiyuan)	1600	1000
Niaosong, undifferentiated	1800	500
Shihshang	1800	600
Daqiuyuan	1800	600
Niaosong (Anzi)	1800	1400
Fulishan	2300	1500
Sanhe	2600	1000
Beiye	2300	1800
Bot. Garden	2300	1800
Damalin (Damalin)	2400	1800
Dahu (Wushantou)	2800	1800

Yingpu (Yingpu)	3200	1600
Yuanshan	3200	2300
Shanjia	3400	1800
Dahu, undifferentiated	3500	1800
Damalin, undifferentiated	3500	1800
Fengbitou	3500	2000
Qilin	3500	2300
Beinan	3500	2300
Damalin (Shuiwaku)	3500	2400
Huakangshan	3500	2500
Dahu (Dahu)	3500	2800
Chihshan Yen	3500	3000
Yingpu (Dingkanzi)	3500	3200
Wanshan	3900	2700
Niumatou	4200	3500
Shuntanpu	4200	3500
Hongmaogang	4200	3500
Niuchouzi	4200	3500
Fushan	4200	3800
Dakeng	4500	3500
Dabengkeng	5000	4200